

Accelerated Fatigue Characterization of Advanced Composites Using Infrared Thermography

Dr. Suhasini Gururaja
Associate Professor

ICCM 24

Baltimore, August 5th, 2025

AEROSPACE ENGINEERING

ADVANCED MATERIALS PROCESSING LAB (AMPL)

**CENTER FOR POLYMERS &
ADVANCED COMPOSITES**

ICAMS

Infrared Thermography – Mean Temperature Rise

- Use temperature as a measure of material degradation - ‘Self-heating’ under cyclic loading
- Staircase loading – constant amplitude loading blocks in increasing fashion
- Cyclic stabilized temp – increases with load level
- Considerably reduced test time and costs

Schematic of the methodology to obtain High Cycle Fatigue Strength (HCFS)
 Montesano et al., CS, 2013

Correlate ΔT_{stab} with σ_{max} to get fatigue limit

Manoharan and Gururaja, *F&FEMS*, 2025 (In Press)

Fatigue testing – Infrared thermography setup

- 100 kN MTS Landmark (Model 370.25) Servo hydraulic test frame
- Telops Spark M150 MWIR camera, InSb cooled
 - 50-mm lens, NETD: 20 mK, 640 x 512 pixels
 - 3-5.4 μm Spectral Range, 15 μm Pitch
- R = 0.1 (tension-tension fatigue)

15 Hz loading frequency

Stepped loading: 5% increase in UTS and 7500 cycle step size

Gage pressure \sim 200 psi

ASTMD638 Type I specimens machined using waterjet – 5 cm gage length

Pathak et al., *Composite Structures*, 2025

Rapid Fatigue Characterization

No-growth limit estimation of CFRP bolted joints (Pristine/BVID)

Additive Manufacturing – Compression Molding (AM-CM)

Can we correlate micro-structure with structural integrity?

Manual AM-CM Process

(Vipin Kumar et. al., ORNL)

Automated AM-CM Process

Pathak et al., *Composite Structures*, 2025

Rapid Fatigue life characterization

Accelerated Life Testing

Pathak et al., *Composite Structures*, 2025

Correlate ΔT_{stab} with σ_{max} to get fatigue limit

Comparison of SN versus ΔT_{stab} fatigue limits

100 TIMES FASTER, WITH 1/6TH OF SPECIMENS REQUIRED!

Baseline tests – pristine specimens (<2% porosity)

Effect of defects

0.9x bead-bead overlap- Without imperfection

1x bead-bead overlap- With imperfection

Imperfections – sites for damage initiation

Process defects in AM-CM composites

*Immersion Ultrasonic C-scan image of AM-CM 20%C/ABS SFT
(Courtesy: Kratos Inc.)*

ASTM D638 Type I specimen dimensions

Microstructural fingerprinting – Ex situ XCT

20 wt.% CF/ABS
997 slices,
Voxel size 0.6 microns

Scanned Volume

Volume for analysis

Microstructural Evolution under cyclic loading

Before test

■ 1.4% Pores

Post-fatigue limit

■ 6.6% Pores

Porosity Distribution with applied loads

- New pores form at fiber ends – due to debonding?
- Pores are found to occur near fiber clusters

Future Work: Multi-scale Framework for AM-SFTs

Conclusions

- Passive Infrared Thermography – Mean Temperature Approach
 - Surface temperature – sentinels of inherent damage
 - Distinctive bi-linear behavior – composite joints, CFRPs, ZT-CFRPs, and others
- Accelerated Qualification of AM components
 - Higher the porosity lower the fatigue limit
- Rapid Fatigue Damage Incipience Identification
 - Hot-spots as heat sources due to process defects
- Ex-situ Micro Computed Tomography
 - Enables quantification of microstructural evolution

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION**

